

Conservation of Momentum in terms of Probability, Space and Time Part II

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In Part i, we argued that not only is conservation of momentum a key principle in classical physics, but its formulation in terms of probability leads to the quantum free particle wavefunction/probability $\exp(ipx)$. In other words, conservation of p is associated with two variables, p and x and an orthogonal function $\exp(ipx)$ (with $\exp(ip2x)$ integrated over x).

In this note, we point out that classically, momentum is conserved in a two body collision while dynamic energy (kinetic energy nonrelativistically) is not if the collision is inelastic. Thus, given a free particle, if one knows its dynamic energy $m_0cc/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and momentum $m_0v/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$, then one may calculate its v and then its m_0 . For conservation of momentum, one only needs to know p , (not E dynamic, m_0 or v). We also note that conservation of momentum follows from action-reaction and Newton's second law which is also formulated in terms of p . Thus, the information related to conservation of momentum is inherent in Newton's second law, but this is a deterministic equation and also requires the idea of action reaction for two particles.

Newton's second law follows from varying a Lagrangian which is written in terms of x, v, t , but we argue that the idea of conservation of momentum should be present even in the Lagrangian or rather the action, which is ultimately varied.. Conservation of momentum only involves the variable p , so we argue that the action should be writable in terms of separate E and p terms (indicating different kinds of conservation), with the latter being linked to momentum conservation. If one uses $v=x/t$, one may write Action = $-Et + px$. Only the px term then should correspond to conservation of momentum, but one sees that one requires two variables, i.e. px . The Action of a free particle is in turn an invariant when seen from different frames moving with constant velocity, where $x/t=v$. Thus, the entire free particle action is an invariant as seen from different frames, but a piece of it is associated with momentum conservation in two body collisions even when E dynamic is not conserved, we argue.

Thus, we suggest that the notion of conservation of momentum is the underlying idea of creating $\exp(ipx)$ as a probability (which yields conservation of momentum), but also in obtaining $\exp(ipx)$ from the action $-Et+px$ or the Lagrange invariant $-Et+px$ (approaches which we have used in previous notes).

Conservation of Momentum and Probability

Newtonian mechanics indicates that momentum should be conserved in a two-body collision using the second law $dp/dt = \text{Force}$ and action-reaction. Dynamic energy (kinetic energy nonrelativistically) is not necessarily conserved.

Given that momentum is conserved, say in a two body collision, (but also in other cases), one may immediately state:

$$\text{Probability}(p_3+p_4 = p_1+p_2) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Probability}(p_3 + p_4 \neq p_1+p_2) = 0 \quad ((1))$$

Here p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4 are vectors. For simplicity one may consider one dimension. Then: $P(p_1)P(p_2)=P(p_1+p_2)$ ((2)), but it is not clear how conservation of momentum ((1)) follows from

this. We argued in Part 1, that one needs to introduce a second variable x and create orthogonal functions based on ((2)) i.e.

$$P(px) = \exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{Then: } \int dx \exp(-ip_3x)\exp(-ip_4x) \exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x) = 0 \text{ if } p_1+p_2 \neq p_3+p_4 \quad ((4))$$

Here we ask: Does one need to integrate over all x ? For $p_1+p_2 = P_a$ and $p_3+p_4=P_b$ one has:

$$0 = \int_{-x_0, x_0} \exp(i (-P_b+P_a) x) \text{ or: } \sin((-P_b+P_a) x_0) = 0$$

$$\text{So } x_0 = 2 \cdot 3.14 / (-P_b+P_a) \quad ((5))$$

Actually, one has $2 \cdot 3.14$ replaced with $2 \cdot 3.14 \hbar$ because one needs a constant which makes px dimensionless. \hbar follows from photon considerations, but here it is simply a constant.

Thus, one does not need to integrate from $-\infty$ to ∞ . If the difference between P_a and P_b is large, then x_0 is very small and vice versa. Thus, if classical physics is associated with large P_a, P_b values, the difference in general will be a large number and x_0 will be very small given the sense of conservation of momentum in a tiny dx region. For smaller P_a, P_b values, x_0 may be considerable to the system size. For example, one may consider a particle in an infinite well.

Thus, creating a probability for p which yields conservation of momentum ultimately requires two variables, px , and leads to $\exp(ipx)$. Thus, there should be two continuity equations, one linked to p and one to x and, as shown in Part I, this is in fact the case for one dimensional photon reflection-refraction.

Link to Classical Action

Conservation of momentum follows in classical physics from Newton's second law and action-reaction. One may obtain Newton's second law from a Lagrangian formalism, but this Lagrangian is a function of x, v and t . Momentum does not require knowledge of m_0 or v , but is mv (nonrelativistically) or $mv / \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ non-relativistically. Conservation of momentum holds if one knows p values. One should be able to write the Lagrangian in terms of x, t, p and E and both relativistically and nonrelativistically one has for $x/t=v$:

$$\text{Action} = Lt = -Et + px \quad ((6))$$

The point we wish to make is that the required information linked to conservation of momentum appears in an isolated term, namely px . For conservation of momentum in a reaction of two particles, E dynamic is not necessarily conserved. Thus, we argue that the physics of conservation of momentum already appears in the isolated px term as a relevant term, but this term contains two variables, p and x . Earlier it was found that px was needed to create $\exp(ipx)$

which in turn allowed for conservation of momentum. The presence of two variables px , but only one, p , in the momentum conservation statement, suggests that perhaps the variable x is integrated out. This might suggest an orthogonal function in p, x with x being integrated. Orthogonal functions in x , however, cannot be strictly positive or negative and so this suggests an altering of sign, i.e. some kind of periodicity.

Link to Special Relativity

The form ((6)) is a Lorentz invariant. In other words if one has a rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at $t=t_0$, then it becomes E', p' at x', t' where $x'/t' = v$.

At first one may state that there is a contradiction between $x=0$ (a sharp point) and $\exp(ipx)$ for $p \rightarrow 0$ i.e. $\hbar/p \rightarrow \infty$. $\hbar/p \rightarrow \infty$ means that the particle may be at any x point, but a rest particle may also be at any x , so it seems there is no contradiction. A Lorentz transformation keeps E and p separate because they are involved in different types of conservation laws, i.e. p conservation in two body collisions does not necessarily mean e conservation, (Total energy is conserved, but not necessarily dynamical energy.) Again, forming a Lorentz invariant involving space yields:

Lorentz invariant: $-Et+px$ ((7))

Even though one may use $x/t=v$ to create a Lorentz transformation, ((7)) is general. Px is again isolated and we argue that this is linked to momentum conservation, a fundamental idea of physics. For a particle with rest mass, p is energy flow and if energy is not being created or disappearing, it should be conserved.

If one creates $\exp(ipx)$ using the px , one sees that one has orthogonal functions in x which allow for momentum conservation. Px is the only information needed for momentum conservation. P by itself does not yield a function which shows momentum conservation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argued in Part I, that the quantum mechanical $\exp(ipx)$, i.e. free particle wavefunction, is really a px dependent probability which ensures momentum conservation for two-body collisions. We argued that one cannot create such a probability using p alone.

In this note, we try to show that the px product of variables, which is linked to conservation of momentum in a probability scenario, is present in both the free particle action, written in terms of t, x, p, E and the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$. In other words, for momentum conservation in two body collisions, one does not necessarily have E conservation (dynamical energy) and one does not need to know m_0 or v , only p . We suggested that the action should split into terms such that momentum conservation is evident and we argue that px is this term. Again, we see that x is needed with p as momentum conservation is created by using orthogonal variables and so p is not enough. x becomes the variable over which one integrates. Only one variable is needed for orthogonality, so x and t appear as if they are independent in $-Et+px$. The same features occur

for the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$. For a particle with rest mass, $p = \text{energy flow}$ and if there is no energy creation or disappearance, energy flow should be conserved. This flow conservation is not the same thing as E conservation, so the flow part of the picture, px , is isolated in both the classical action and Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$.